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Objective reality and probability

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

In discussing the role of causation in science, it is necessary to rely on logically consistent (mathematical-scientific) methods.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The most basic methods of statistics and probability theory were used.

RESULTS:

The probability of an event is determined by the variance of an event and the expectation value of an event.

CONCLUSION:

Probability and causation does not exclude each other.

Keywords:

Induction; Deduction; Probability; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Mathematical methods should be of use to relate facts and hypotheses of a particular kind in the light of empirical facts. The data as recordings of individual observations or events obtained by an experiment or in a scientific study from a population, called the sample, should help us to determine whether we may rely on a certain hypothesis or how strong does the data support the hypothesis, and so on. It is insightful to view mathematics as one response to David Hume's approach to the method of induction^{1, 2} (David Hume, 1739, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, Book 1, part iii, section 6). It surely makes sense to ask whether the doubts on inductive inference as raised Hume are justified. But the answer to Hume's problem of induction is fairly straightforward. One might, for instance, expect that statistical methods are able to dismantle Humean circularity on induction and do justify predictions or expectations even about observations we have not yet made, as well as claims which might go even beyond the observed especially on the basis of inductive inferences. In the meantime, various statistical methods and measures of relationship have been developed, view of them have a very long history. The arithmetic mean³ has already been studied by the Pythagoreans⁴ in Antiquity.

¹Sloman, S. A., & Lagnado, D. A. (2005). "The Problem of Induction". In K. J. Holyoak & R. G. Morrison (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of thinking and reasoning* (pp. 95–116). Cambridge University Press.

²Lange, Marc. "Hume and the Problem of Induction." *Handbook of the History of Logic*. Vol. 10. North-Holland, 2011. 43-91.

³William Hunt Gauger, *The Gaugers magazine wherein the foundation of his art is briefly explain'd and illustrated with such figures as may render the whole intelligible to a mean capacity*, Printed by Mary Clark, London: 1687; pp. 308.

⁴Heath, Thomas Little. *A history of Greek mathematics*. Vol. 1. Oxford: At the Clarendon Press, 1921.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definitions

2.1.1. Trial t

Definition 2.1 (Trial).

Let t denote a random event, a trial, a run of an experiment et cetera at a certain (period of) time t .

$$t = \{0, 1, \dots\} \quad (1)$$

At every trial t , a certain event either occurred or did not occur (complementary event). A negative t is possible too.

Example.

A toss of a fair coin is a (Bernoulli) trial with a probability of heads = 0.5.

2.1.2. Principle of Superposition

Definition 2.2 (Principle of Superposition).

Let ${}_R U_t$ denote a set of all possible individual (discrete or continuous) outcomes ${}_R U_{it}$ of an experiment (sample space), a measurable parameter in a physical system, a (quantum mechanical) entity or an (quantum mechanical) observable, a random variable et cetera. Let ${}_R U_{it}$ denote the possible value, a/an (quantum mechanical) observable can take, an eigenvalue of a/an (quantum mechanical) operator. In general, we consider ${}_R U_t$ as being in a state of superposition at certain (Bernoulli) trial t as

$${}_R U_t = {}_R U_{1t} + {}_R U_{2t} + \dots + {}_R U_{kt} = ({}_R U_1 + {}_R U_2 + \dots + {}_R U_k)_t = \sum_{i=1}^k U_{it} \quad (2)$$

After N (Bernoulli) trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45), we obtain

$${}_R U_N = \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^k U_{it} \quad (3)$$

and equally

$${}_R U_N^y = \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^k U_{it}^y \quad (4)$$

The principle of superposition is a natural law which has been proposed by the Danish geologist Nicolaus Steno (see [Stenonis, Nicolai, 1669](#)) in his 1696 book ‘De Solido Intra Naturaliter Contento Dissertationis Prodomus’ and has many applications in science. In the following, **the superposition principle** has been re-stated by Daniel Bernoulli (1700 – 1782) in 1753 (“**Later (1753), Daniel Bernoulli formulated the principle of superposition ...**”(see [Brillouin, Leon, 1946](#), p. 2)) too.

Example.

In quantum mechanics, every experimental measurable $R U_{it}$ is the eigenvalue of a specific operator $R U_t$. The $R U_{it}$ eigenvalues represents the possible measured values of the $R U_t$ operator. Corresponding to each eigenvalue is a/an (eigen or probability et cetera) function. Under conditions where the eigenvalues $R U_{it}$ are discrete, the (physical) variable is said to be quantized while the index i plays the role of a quantum number which characterizes a certain quantum state.

2.1.3. Arithmetic mean of a single value $R U_i$

A certain value of an entity $R U_i$ can be found several times within a population or a sample size N . It is (see also equation 16)

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N R U_i \right) = R U_i + R U_i + \dots + R U_i = \frac{E(R U_i)}{p(R U_i)} + \frac{E(R U_i)}{p(R U_i)} + \dots + \frac{E(R U_i)}{p(R U_i)} = N \times p(\bar{R U}_i) \times R U_i \quad (5)$$

while N is the sample or populations size, $p(\bar{R U}_i)$ is the probability of the single value U_i , $E(R U_i)$ is the expectation value of the single value U_i , $p(\bar{R U}_i)$ is the relative frequency of the single value U_i .

EXAMPLE

$$\begin{aligned} & 3 + 3 + 3 \\ & \equiv \underbrace{(1 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0)}_{\text{Sample size } N} \times 3 \\ & \equiv \underbrace{(3)}_{\text{Absolute frequency}} \times 3 \\ & \equiv 9 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In general, the mean value of such an entity $R U_i$ is given as

$$\bar{R U}_i = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N R U_i \right) = \frac{R U_i + R U_i + \dots + R U_i}{N} = \frac{E(R U_i)}{N \times p(R U_i)} + \frac{E(R U_i)}{N \times p(R U_i)} + \dots + \frac{E(R U_i)}{N \times p(R U_i)} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, from equation 7 follows (see equation 16) that

$$\left(\sum_{t=1}^N {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i \right) = N \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i = N \times p({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i) \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i \quad (8)$$

or that

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i = p({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i) \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i \quad (9)$$

or that

$$\frac{1}{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i} = \frac{p({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i)}{{}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i} \quad (10)$$

and at the end that

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i = \left(\frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i}{p({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i)} \right) \quad (11)$$

2.1.4. Absolute frequency

Definition 2.3 (Absolute frequency).

The absolute frequency of an event ${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i$, denoted by $N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i)$, is the number of times an event with the same property has occurred/recorded or has been observed in a (random) experiment or a study of the sample size $N = N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t)$. In general, it is

$$N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t) = N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_1) + N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_2) + \dots + N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_k) = \sum_{i=1}^k N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i) \quad (12)$$

Normalising equation before (see eq. 12) it is

$$\frac{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_1)}{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t)} + \dots + \frac{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_k)}{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t)} = +1 \quad (13)$$

and equally

$$N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i) = N({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t) \times \left(1 - \frac{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i)}{N({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t)} \right) = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i)}{({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i)} \quad (14)$$

2.1.5. Relative frequency

Definition 2.4 (Relative frequency).

The relative frequency (or empirical probability) of an event is the absolute frequency of an event divided by the total number of events, i.e. by the sample size N . The abbreviation of the relative frequency (see von Mises, 1927) or necessity is $p(\bar{R}U_i)$. In general, it is

$$p(\bar{R}U_i) = \frac{N(\bar{R}U_i)}{N} = \frac{N(\bar{R}U_i)}{N(\bar{R}U_t)} = \frac{N(\bar{R}U_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^k N(\bar{R}U_i)} = \frac{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{R}U_i)}{(\bar{R}U_i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{R}U_i)}{(\bar{R}U_i)}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{R}U_i)}{N \times (\bar{R}U_i)} = \frac{(\bar{R}U_i)}{(\bar{R}U_i)} \quad (15)$$

where $N(\bar{R}U_i)$ is the absolute frequency of an event $\bar{R}U_i$, the number of times an event with the same property has occurred/recorded or has been observed in a (random) experiment or a study of the sample size $N = N(\bar{R}U_t)$, while N is the sample or populations size, $p(\bar{R}U_i)$ is the relative frequency of the single value U_i and $(\bar{R}U_i)$ is the mean value of the the single value U_i . From equation 15 follows that

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{R}U_i) = N \times p(\bar{R}U_i) \times (\bar{R}U_i) = N \times p(\bar{R}U_i) \times \frac{E(\bar{R}U_i)}{p(\bar{R}U_i)} \quad (16)$$

where $p(\bar{R}U_i)$ is the probability of the single value U_i , $E(\bar{R}U_i)$ is the expectation value of the single value U_i . Simplifying equation 16, it is (see equation 7)

$$\bar{R}U_i = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \bar{R}U_i \right) = \frac{\bar{R}U_i + \bar{R}U_i + \dots + \bar{R}U_i}{N} = p(\bar{R}U_i) \times (\bar{R}U_i) = p(\bar{R}U_i) \times \frac{E(\bar{R}U_i)}{p(\bar{R}U_i)} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\bar{R}U_i \times p(\bar{R}U_i) = p(\bar{R}U_i) \times E(\bar{R}U_i) \quad (18)$$

and equally

$$p(\bar{R}U_i) = \left(\frac{p(\bar{R}U_i)}{\bar{R}U_i} \right) \times E(\bar{R}U_i) \quad (19)$$

Equation 19 does not exclude circumstances where $\left(\frac{p(\bar{R}U_i)}{\bar{R}U_i} \right) = +1$. Nonetheless, under conditions

where $\bar{R}U_i = E(\bar{R}U_i)$ it is $p(\bar{R}U_i) = p(\bar{R}U_i)$ but not in general. In some contrast to the lines before, the Austrian scientist and mathematician Richard Edler von Mises (1883 - 1953) claimed that

“Wahrscheinlichkeit eines Ereignisses (ist, author) ...
der Grenzwert der relativen Häufigkeit seines Eintretens. ”

(see von Mises, 1927, p. 502)

or ‘... the probability of an event [is, author] ... the limit value of the relative frequency of its occurrence.’ (see von Mises, 1927, p. 502). Von Mises concept of probability a something like a limit of an infinite sequence has been heavily criticized by Korch (see Korch, 1965, p. 219).

EXAMPLE

A standard 6-sided fair die (plural 'dice'), with an equally likely chance ($p = 1/6$) of landing on any face, is thrown in the air.

Table 1. Example. A standard 6-sided fair die experiment.

Die RU - Number RU_i :	1	2	3	4	5	6
Collumn:	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Bernoulli trial t						
1	0	0	3	0	0	0
2	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	3	0	0	0
4	0	2	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	3	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	4	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	5	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	6
9	0	0	0	0	5	0
10	0	0	0	4	0	0
Sample size $N = 10$						
$\left(\sum_{t=1}^N RU_i\right) =$	1	2	9	8	10	6
Absolute frequency: $N(RU_i) = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (RU_i)}{(RU_i)}$						
	$\frac{1}{1} = 1$	$\frac{2}{2} = 1$	$\frac{9}{3} = 3$	$\frac{8}{4} = 2$	$\frac{10}{5} = 2$	$\frac{6}{6} = 1$
Relative frequency: $p(\overline{RU_i}) = \frac{N(RU_i)}{N}$						
	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{3}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$

2.1.6. Relative frequency of two or more random variables

Definition 2.5 (Relative frequency of two or more random variables).

The relative frequency (or empirical probability) of two or more joint event is the absolute frequency of two or more joint events divided by the total number of two or more joint events, i.e. by the sample size N . The abbreviation of the joint relative frequency (see [von Mises, 1927](#)) or necessity is

$p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j)$. In general, it is

$$p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) = \frac{N(RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{N} = \frac{N(RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^k N(RU_i \wedge RW_j)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^k N(RU_i \wedge RW_j)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{N} \quad (20)$$

From equation 20 follows that

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (RU_i \wedge RW_j) = N \times p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times (RU_i \wedge RW_j) = N \times p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times \frac{E(RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{p(RU_i \wedge RW_j)} \quad (21)$$

Simplifying equation 21, it is (see equation 7)

$$(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (RU_i \wedge RW_j) \right) = p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times (RU_i \wedge RW_j) = p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times \frac{E(RU_i \wedge RW_j)}{p(RU_i \wedge RW_j)} \quad (22)$$

or

$$(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times p(RU_i \wedge RW_j) = p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) \times E(RU_i \wedge RW_j) \quad (23)$$

and equally

$$p(RU_i \wedge RW_j) = \left(\frac{p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j)}{(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j)} \right) \times E(RU_i \wedge RW_j) \quad (24)$$

Equation 24 does not exclude circumstances where $\left(\frac{p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j)}{(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j)} \right) = +1$. Thus far, under conditions where $(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) = E(RU_i \wedge RW_j)$ it is $p(\overline{R}U_i \wedge \overline{R}W_j) = p(RU_i \wedge RW_j)$ but not in general.

EXAMPLE. TWO DICE EXPERIMENT

Table 2. Example. Two standard 6-sided fair dice experiment.

Die ${}_R U$ - Number ${}_R U_i$:	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Die ${}_R W$ - Number ${}_R W_j$:							(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	$((3) \times (9))$
Collumn:	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)							
Bernoulli trial t													
1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	9
2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	9
4	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0
5	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	9
6	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0
Sample size N = 10													
$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N {}_R U_i\right) =$	1	2	9	8	10	6							
$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N {}_R W_i\right) =$							1	4	9	8	5	6	
$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N ({}_R U_i \times {}_R W_j)\right) =$													27
Absolute frequency: $N({}_R U_i) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ({}_R U_i)}{({}_R U_i)}$	$\frac{1}{1} = 1$	$\frac{2}{2} = 1$	$\frac{9}{3} = 3$	$\frac{8}{4} = 2$	$\frac{10}{5} = 2$	$\frac{6}{6} = 1$							
Relative frequency: $p({}_R \bar{U}_i) = \frac{N({}_R U_i)}{N}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{3}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$							
Absolute frequency: $N({}_R W_j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ({}_R W_j)}{({}_R W_j)}$	$\frac{1}{1} = 1$	$\frac{4}{2} = 2$	$\frac{9}{3} = 3$	$\frac{8}{4} = 2$	$\frac{5}{5} = 1$	$\frac{6}{6} = 1$							
Relative frequency: $p({}_R \bar{W}_j) = \frac{N({}_R W_j)}{N}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{3}{10}$	$\frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{1}{10}$							
Absolute frequency: $N({}_R U_i \wedge {}_R W_j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ({}_R U_i \times {}_R W_j)}{({}_R U_i \times {}_R W_j)}$													$\frac{27}{9} = 3$
Relative frequency: $p({}_R \bar{U}_i \wedge {}_R \bar{W}_j) = \frac{N({}_R U_i \wedge {}_R W_j)}{N}$													$\frac{3}{10}$

2.1.7. Arithmetic mean in General

Definition 2.6 (Arithmetic mean).

Suppose that the theoretically possible random events ${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{1t}, {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{2t}, \dots, {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{kt}$ form a random variable ${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t$ et cetera. Let ${}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t$ represent the arithmetic average of these theoretically possible k states/events. Thus,

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t = \frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t}{N} = \frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{1t} + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{2t} + \dots + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{kt}}{N} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k U_{it}}{N} \quad (25)$$

It is

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t = N \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t \quad (26)$$

The average value, or sample mean, after N runs of an experiment, is

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_N = \frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_N}{N} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^k U_{it}}{N} \quad (27)$$

The sample mean is a random variable which converges according to the law of large numbers to the expected value as the sample size N goes to positive infinity ($N \rightarrow +\infty$).

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i = \sum_{t=1}^N U_{it} \quad (28)$$

or

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}U^y_i = \sum_{t=1}^N U^y_{it} \quad (29)$$

and equally

$${}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i = \frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i}{N} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N U_{it}}{N} \quad (30)$$

2.1.8. Expected value

An expected value (see [Huygens and van Schooten, 1657](#); [Whitworth, 1901](#)) of something like a random variable (with a finite number of outcomes), also called mean, average, mathematical expectation, expectation, expectancy et cetera, is something like a generalization of a weighted average. The expectation value, denoted as $E({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t)$, is defined as

$$E({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t) = p({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t) \times ({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t) = E({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{1t} + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{2t} + \dots + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{kt}) = E({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{1t}) + \dots + E({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{kt}) \quad (31)$$

Equally, it is

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t^2\right) = p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) \times \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t^2\right) \quad (32)$$

The expectation value of the mean, denoted as $E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right)$, is defined as

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right) = \frac{1}{N} \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) = \frac{E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)}{N} = E\left(\frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t}{N}\right) = \frac{E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{1t} + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{2t} + \dots + {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_{kt}\right)}{N} \quad (33)$$

while the expectation value as such, denoted as $E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)$, is given as

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) = \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) = \Psi\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) \times \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) \times \Psi^*\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) \quad (34)$$

where $\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)$ is the random variable et cetera and $p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)$ the probability of the random variable et cetera, $\Psi\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)$ is the wave-function and $\Psi^*\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)$ is the complex conjugate of a certain wave-function. In general, it is

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) = N \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right) \quad (35)$$

and

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right)^2 = N^2 \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right)^2 \quad (36)$$

and

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t^2\right) = {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t\right) = N \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right) = N \times N \times {}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t \times E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t\right) \quad (37)$$

In general, we define that

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_t^2\right) \equiv \frac{E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_t^2\right)}{N} \quad (38)$$

The expectation value of a single value ${}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i$ is given as

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) = \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) = \left(\frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i}{p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i\right)}\right) \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) \quad (39)$$

and as

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right)^2 = \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right)^2 \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i}{p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i\right)}\right)^2 \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right)^2 \quad (40)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$E\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i^2\right) = \left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right)^2 \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) = \left(\frac{{}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i}{p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}\bar{U}_i\right)}\right)^2 \times p\left({}_{\mathbf{R}}U_i\right) \quad (41)$$

The variance $\sigma({}_R U_i)^2$ of a single value ${}_R U_i$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma({}_R U_i)^2 & \equiv E({}_R U_i^2) - E({}_R U_i)^2 \\
 & \equiv E({}_R U_i) \times E(\overline{{}_R U_i}) \\
 & \equiv ({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R U_i) \times ({}_R U_i) \times (1 - p({}_R U_i)) \\
 & \equiv ({}_R U_i)^2 \times p({}_R U_i) \times (1 - p({}_R U_i)) \\
 & \equiv \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right)^2 \times p({}_R U_i) \times (1 - p({}_R U_i))
 \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

The co-variance $\sigma({}_R U_i, {}_R W_j)$ of single values ${}_R U_i$ and ${}_R W_j$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma({}_R U_i, {}_R W_j) & \equiv E({}_R U_i \wedge {}_R W_j) - (E({}_R U_i) \times E({}_R W_j)) \\
 & \equiv ({}_R U_i \times {}_R W_j) \times (p({}_R U_i \wedge {}_R W_j) - (p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j))) \\
 & \equiv \left(\frac{({}_R \bar{U}_i) \times ({}_R \bar{W}_j)}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i) \times p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \times (p({}_R U_i \wedge {}_R W_j) - (p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j)))
 \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$p({}_R U_i) = p({}_R U_i) \tag{44}$$

or

$$(({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R U_i)) = (({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R U_i)) \tag{45}$$

and

$$(({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R U_i)) \times (({}_R W_j) \times p({}_R W_j)) = (({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R U_i)) \times (({}_R W_j) \times p({}_R W_j)) \tag{46}$$

In other words, it is

$$({}_R U_i) \times ({}_R W_j) \times p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j) = ({}_R U_i) \times ({}_R W_j) \times p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j) \tag{47}$$

With respect to equation 11, equation 47 becomes

$$\left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right) \times \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \times p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j) = \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right) \times \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \times p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j) \tag{48}$$

Rearranging equation 48, it is

$$\left(\left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right) \times \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \right) \times (p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j) - p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j)) = 0 = \tag{49}$$

or

$$\left(\frac{(\overline{R}U_i) \times (\overline{R}W_j)}{p(\overline{R}U_i) \times p(\overline{R}W_j)} \right) \times (p({}_{R}U_i) \times p({}_{R}W_j) - p({}_{R}U_i) \times p({}_{R}W_j)) = 0 \quad (50)$$

In the case of independence, it is $p(({}_{R}U_i) \wedge ({}_{R}W_j)) = p({}_{R}U_i) \times p({}_{R}W_j)$. Equation 50 becomes

$$\sigma({}_{R}U_i, {}_{R}W_j) = \left(\frac{(\overline{R}U_i) \times (\overline{R}W_j)}{p(\overline{R}U_i) \times p(\overline{R}W_j)} \right) \times (p(({}_{R}U_i) \wedge ({}_{R}W_j)) - p({}_{R}U_i) \times p({}_{R}W_j)) = 0 \quad (51)$$

□

2.1.9. The n-th moment expectation value of U

Definition 2.7 (The n-th moment expectation value of U). Let ${}_{R}U_{it}$ denote an event at a certain (period of) time or **Bernoulli trial** t (Uspensky, 1937). Let $p({}_{R}U_{it})$ represent the probability of an event at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_{R}U_{it}^n)$ denote the n -th moment **expectation value** (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Whitworth, 1901) of ${}_{R}U_{it}$. Let $E({}_{R}U_{it}^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_{R}U_{it}$. Let $E({}_{R}U_{it}^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of ${}_{R}U_{it}$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_{R}U_{it}$ is defined as**

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_{R}U_{it}^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times {}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times {}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_{R}U_{it}) \\ &\equiv ({}_{R}U_{it}^n) \times p({}_{R}U_{it}) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_{R}U_{it}^n)^m &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times {}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times {}_{R}U_{it}^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right)^m \times p({}_{R}U_{it})^m \\ &\equiv ({}_{R}U_{it}^n)^m \times p({}_{R}U_{it})^m \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_{R}U_{it}$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_{R}U_{it}^1) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_{R}U_{it}^1}_{(one\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_{R}U_{it}) \\ &\equiv ({}_{R}U_{it}^1) \times p({}_{R}U_{it}) \\ &\equiv ({}_{R}U_{it}) \times p({}_{R}U_{it}) \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

The second moment expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_{it}^2) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R U_{it}^1}_{(two-times)} \right) \times p({}_R U_{it}) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_{it}^2) \times p({}_R U_{it}) \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

2.1.10. The n-th moment expectation value of anti U

Definition 2.8 (The n-th moment expectation value of anti U). Let $p({}_R U_{it})$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R U_{it}$ at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $(1-p({}_R U_{it}))$ represent the probability that a single event ${}_R U_{it}$ will not occur, will not exist at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^n)$ denote the n-th moment **expectation value** (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Whitworth, 1901) of anti ${}_R U_{it}$. Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_{it}$. Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_{it}$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_{it}$** is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R U_{it}^1 \times \dots}_{(n-times)} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \\ &\equiv ({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^n) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

The first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_{it}$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^1) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_{it}^1}_{(one-times)} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \\ &\equiv ({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^1) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_{it}) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

The second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_{it}$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^2) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R U_{it}^1}_{(two-times)} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \\ &\equiv ({}_R \underline{U}_{it}^2) \times (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

2.1.11. The n-th moment expectation value of U and W

Definition 2.9 (The n-th moment expectation value of U and W). Let $p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t)$ represent the joint probability of an occurring of the events ${}_R U_{it}$ and ${}_R W_t$ at the same (period of time or) Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_{it}^n, {}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$ and ${}_R W_t$. Let $E({}_R U_{it}^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$ and ${}_R W_t$ is defined as**

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_{it}^n, {}_R W_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{({}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times ({}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_{it}^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$ and ${}_R W_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_{it}^1, {}_R W_t^1) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R W_t^1}_{(one\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_{it}^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_{it} \times {}_R W_t) \times p({}_R U_{it}, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

2.1.12. The probability of a single event

Definition 2.10 (The probability of a single event). In consideration of the definitions before, again let $p({}_R U_{it})$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R U_{it}$ at Bernoulli trial t . Let $\Psi({}_R U_{it})$ represent the wavefunction, a probability amplitude (Born, 1926) of an event or of finding an event inside a set at a given (period of) time / Bernoulli trial (Uspensky, 1937) t . Let $\Psi^*({}_R U_{it})$ denote the complex conjugate of the wave-function. In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned} p({}_R U_{it}) &\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_{it})}{{}_R U_{it}} \\ &\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_{it})^2}{E({}_R U_{it}^2)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p({}_R U_{it})^2 \times ({}_R U_{it})^2}{p({}_R U_{it}) \times ({}_R U_{it})^2} \\ &\equiv \Psi({}_R U_{it}) \times \Psi^*({}_R U_{it}) \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

2.1.13. Wave function

Definition 2.11 (Wave function). Taking into account especially the definitions before and the relationship that $p({}_R U_{it}) \equiv \Psi({}_R U_{it}) \times \Psi^*({}_R U_{it})$, some other relationships can be derived too. Recall again that $p({}_R U_{it})$ represent the probability of a certain single event at the Bernoulli trial t , $\Psi({}_R U_{it})$ represent the wave function, a probability amplitude (Born, 1926) of an event at a given (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t and $\Psi^*({}_R U_{it})$ is the complex conjugate of the wave-function of ${}_R U_{it}$. Let $f({}_R U_{it})$ denote any kind of a mathematical function which describes the behaviour of ${}_R U_{it}$ while the same mathematical function satisfies the need that $\frac{f({}_R U_{it})}{f({}_R U_{it})} \equiv +1$. In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi({}_R U_{it}) &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*({}_R U_{it})} \times p({}_R U_{it}) \\
 &\equiv \frac{p({}_R U_{it})}{\Psi^*({}_R U_{it} \times f({}_R U_{it}))} \times f({}_R U_{it}) \\
 &\equiv \frac{p({}_R U_{it})}{\underbrace{\Psi^*({}_R U_{it}) \times f({}_R U_{it})}_Z} \times f({}_R U_{it}) \\
 &\equiv Z \times f({}_R U_{it}) \\
 &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*({}_R U_{it})} \times \frac{E({}_R U_{it})}{{}_R U_{it}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*({}_R U_{it}) \times {}_R U_{it}} \times E({}_R U_{it})
 \end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

Under conditions where ${}_o U_{it}$ and ${}_o \underline{U}_{it}$ are described by a wave-function, it is $\Psi({}_o U_{it}) + \Psi({}_o \underline{U}_{it}) \equiv \Psi({}_o U_{it} + {}_o \underline{U}_{it}) \equiv \Psi({}_R U_{it})$ while the normalisation condition is necessary to be ensured.

2.1.14. The complex conjugate

Definition 2.12 (The complex conjugate). The conjugate of a complex number denoted as conjugate $(a({}_R U_{it}) + (i \times b({}_R U_{it})))$, where $i^2 \equiv -1$ is the imaginary (Bombelli, 1579), is defined as

$$\text{conjugate}(a({}_R U_{it}) + (i \times b({}_R U_{it}))) \equiv (a({}_R U_{it}) - (i \times b({}_R U_{it}))) \tag{63}$$

It is known that any complex number multiplied by its complex conjugate is a real number. It is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a({}_R U_{it}) + (i \times b({}_R U_{it}))) \times (a({}_R U_{it}) - (i \times b({}_R U_{it}))) &\equiv (a({}_R U_{it})^2) - (i^2 \times b({}_R U_{it})^2) \\
 &\equiv (a({}_R U_{it})^2) + (b({}_R U_{it})^2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

2.1.15. The variance

Definition 2.13 (Variance).

Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890 – 1962), an English statistician, “the single most important figure in 20th century statistics”(Efron, 1998) coined the term variance as follows: “It is therefore desirable **in analysing the causes** of variability to deal with the square of the standard deviation as the measure of variability. We shall term this quantity the Variance ... ” (see Fisher, Ronald Aylmer, 1919, p. 399) In general, variance is defined (see Kolmogorov, 1956, p. 42) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma({}_R U_t)^2 &\equiv \sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R U_t) \\
 &\equiv E({}_R U_t - E({}_R U_t))^2 \\
 &\equiv E({}_R U_t^2) - (E({}_R U_t))^2 \\
 &\equiv ({}_R U_t^2 \times p({}_R U_t)) - (p({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t)^2 \\
 &\equiv ({}_R U_t^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) - p({}_R U_t)^2) \\
 &\equiv ({}_R U_t^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \\
 &\equiv {}_R U_t \times (p({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \\
 &\equiv E({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t)) \\
 &\equiv E({}_R U_t) \times E(\underline{{}_R U_t})
 \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

It follows that

$$\sigma(\overline{{}_R U_t})^2 \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2}{N} \tag{66}$$

Again, let $p({}_R U_{it})$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R U_{it}$ at a given point in space-time or Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_{it})$ denote again the expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$. The expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}$ is defined as

$$E({}_R U_{it}) \equiv p({}_R U_{it}) \times ({}_R U_{it}) \equiv \Psi({}_R U_{it}) \times {}_R U_{it} \times \Psi^*({}_R U_{it}) \tag{67}$$

The expectation value of the other of ${}_R U_{it}$, of the complementary of ${}_R U_{it}$, of the opposite of ${}_R U_{it}$, of **the anti** ${}_R U_{it}$, denoted by $\underline{{}_R U_{it}}$, is defined as

$$E(\underline{{}_R U_{it}}) \equiv (1 - p({}_R U_{it})) \times ({}_R U_{it}) \tag{68}$$

In this context, $E({}_R U_{it}^2)$ is the expectation value of the second moment of ${}_R U_{it}$. The expectation value of ${}_R U_{it}^2$ is defined as

$$E({}_R U_{it}^2) \equiv p({}_R U_{it}) \times ({}_R U_{it}^2) \equiv p({}_R U_{it}) \times ({}_R U_{it} \times {}_R U_{it}) \tag{69}$$

Let $\sigma({}_R U_{it})$ denote the standard deviation of ${}_R U_{it}$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_{it})^2$ denote the variance of ${}_R U_{it}$. In general,

the variance (see [Kolmogorov, 1956](#), p. 42) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma(\mathbf{R}U_{it})^2 &\equiv \sigma(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times \sigma(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \\
 &\equiv E(\mathbf{R}U_{it} - E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))^2 \\
 &\equiv E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2) - (E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))^2 \\
 &\equiv (\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2 \times p(\mathbf{R}U_{it})) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times \mathbf{R}U_{it})^2 \\
 &\equiv (\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it})^2) \\
 &\equiv (\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))) \\
 &\equiv \mathbf{R}U_{it} \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times \mathbf{R}U_{it} \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))) \\
 &\equiv E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times \mathbf{R}U_{it} \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it})) \\
 &\equiv E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times E(\mathbf{R}U_{it})
 \end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

From equation 70 follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it})) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_{it})^2}{\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2} \\
 &\equiv \frac{E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2) - (E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))^2}{\mathbf{R}U_{it}^2} \\
 &\equiv \frac{E(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times E(\mathbf{R}U_{it})}{\mathbf{R}U_{it} \times \mathbf{R}U_{it}} \\
 &\equiv p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it})^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

and equally (Eq. 70) that

$$\mathbf{R}U_{it} \equiv \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_{it})}{\sqrt{p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_{it}))}} \tag{72}$$

and that

$$\mathbf{R}W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{R}W_t)}{\sqrt{p(\mathbf{R}W_t) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_t))}} \tag{73}$$

2.1.16. $\tilde{\chi}^2$ Goodness of fit test

Definition 2.14 ($\tilde{\chi}^2$ Goodness of fit test).

The amount by which a random variable $\mathbf{R}U_t$ varies from its own expectation value $E(\mathbf{R}U_t)$ can be measured by the chi square distribution. **The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test** is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\chi}^2({}_R U_t) &\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_t - E({}_R U_t))^2}{E({}_R U_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2}{E({}_R U_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_t) \times E({}_R U_{it})}{E({}_R U_t)} \equiv E({}_R U_{it}) \equiv {}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))
\end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

where ${}_R U_t$ is the random variable observed et cetera, $E({}_R U_t)$ is the random variable expected and $\sigma({}_R U_t)^2$ is the variance of the random variable. Yate's [Yates \(1934\)](#) continuity correction has not been considered. The z-score, denoted as $Z({}_R U_t)$, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
Z^2({}_R U_t) &\equiv \frac{({}_R U_t - E({}_R U_t))^2}{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2} = \frac{({}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t)))^2}{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2} \\
&\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_t)^2}{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2} \\
&\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_{it})^2}{E({}_R U_t) \times E({}_R U_{it})} = \frac{E({}_R U_{it})}{E({}_R U_t)} = \frac{1 - p({}_R U_t)}{p({}_R U_t)}
\end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

It follows that

$$Z^2({}_R U_t) \equiv \frac{\tilde{\chi}^2({}_R U_t)}{E({}_R U_t)} \tag{76}$$

and that

$$\tilde{\chi}^2({}_R U_t) \equiv E({}_R U_t) \times Z^2({}_R U_t) \tag{77}$$

2.2. Material

2.3. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*⁵ too.

⁵Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

3. Results

3.1. The exact probability of an event

Theorem 1 (Anti Chebyshev - The Chebyshev equality). *Pafnuty Lvovich Chebyshev's (1821 – 1894) inequality (also called the Irénée-Jules Bienaymé [Bienaymé \(1853\)](#) (1796 – 1878) – Chebyshev inequality) holds for any distribution as long as the distribution includes a defined mean and variance. Under these circumstances, Chebyshev's inequality gives a rather crude upper bound on the probability that a random variable ${}_R U_t$ will be more than a specified distance from its mean $E({}_R U_t)$. This is often useful under conditions where the distribution is unknown, but the mean and variance are known (at least approximately). In accordance with the Chebyshev's inequality, within two standard deviations away from the mean 75% of the values, and within three standard deviations away from the mean 88.9% of the values will be found. Nonetheless, Chebyshev's inequality is less precise than the 65-95-99.7 % rule of the normal distribution. In the following, we shall rely on Kolmogoroff's expositions on Chebyshev's inequality. Chebyshev's inequality is defined (see [Kolmogorov, 1956](#), p. 42) as*

$$p\left(|{}_R U_t - E({}_R U_t)| \geq \sqrt{E({}_R U_t^2)}\right) \leq \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2}{E({}_R U_t^2)} \quad (78)$$

However, it is necessary to emphasize that Chebyshev's inequality as proved by Chebyshev ([Tschébychef, 1867](#)) himself in 1867 and later by his student Andrey Markov (1856–1922) in his 1884 Ph.D. thesis does not provide us with **an exact probability value of a random variable**. Thus far and in contrast to Chebyshev's inequality (see [Kolmogorov, 1956](#), p. 42), the exact value of the probability of an event, anti Chebyshev's inequality or (**Chebyshev's equality**), is given by the relationship

$$p({}_R U_t) \equiv 1 - \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2}{E({}_R U_t^2)} \quad (79)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{\text{(Premise)}} \quad (80)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$p({}_R U_t) \equiv 1 - \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2}{E({}_R U_t^2)} \quad (81)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (82)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise (i. e. axiom) by the variance $\sigma({}_R U_t)^2$

$$\sigma({}_R U_t)^2 \equiv \sigma({}_R U_t)^2 \quad (83)$$

Equation 83 can be rearranged (see definition 2.13, equation 65) as

$$E({}_R U_t^2) - (E({}_R U_t))^2 \equiv \sigma({}_R U_t)^2 \quad (84)$$

or as

$$E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right) \equiv \left(E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)^2 + \sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2 \quad (85)$$

The normalised form of the variance follows as

$$\frac{\left(E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} + \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \equiv +1 \quad (86)$$

Rearranging equation 86, it is

$$\frac{\left(E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \equiv 1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \quad (87)$$

Equation 87 simplifies (see equation 32) as

$$\frac{\left(E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \equiv \frac{\left(\left({}_{R}U_t\right) \times p\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)^2}{\left(\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right) \times p\left({}_{R}U_t\right)\right)} \equiv 1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \quad (88)$$

Equation 88 simplifies slightly. In general, the variance and the expected value of a random variable are theoretically capable of determining the exact value of the probability of an event as

$$p\left({}_{R}U_t\right) \equiv 1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \quad (89)$$

□

3.2. Probability of an event and the standard error of the mean

The sampling distribution of a mean of a random variable might be obtained by repeated sampling from a certain population. Mathematically, the variance of the sampling mean distribution $\sigma\left({}_{R}\bar{U}_t\right)^2$ obtained by experiments or a study is equal to the variance of the population $\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2$ divided by the sample size N. The standard error of the mean (SEM) for a given sample size is defined as the standard deviation divided by the square root of the sample size. These basic relationships might enable us to calculate the exact probability of an event as follows.

Theorem 2 (Probability and the standard error of the mean). *In general, the exact probability of an event is determined by the following relationship too.*

$$p\left({}_{R}U_t\right) = 1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}\bar{U}_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}\bar{U}_t^2\right)} \quad (90)$$

Proof by direct proof. In accordance with our previous findings (see equation 31 and equation 79), it is

$$p\left({}_{R}U_t\right) = \frac{E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)}{\left({}_{R}U_t\right)} = \frac{E\left({}_{R}U_t\right) \times E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)}{\left({}_{R}U_t\right) \times E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)} = \frac{E\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} = 1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_{R}U_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_{R}U_t^2\right)} \quad (91)$$

Equation before can be rearranged as follows.

$$p(\text{R}U_t) = 1 - \frac{(N) \times \sigma(\text{R}U_t)^2}{(N) \times E(\text{R}U_t^2)} = 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma(\text{R}U_t)^2}{N} \times \frac{N}{E(\text{R}U_t^2)} \right) \quad (92)$$

It is known that $\sigma(\text{R}\bar{U}_t)^2 \equiv \frac{\sigma(\text{R}U_t)^2}{N}$ (see equation 66) and that $E(\text{R}\bar{U}_t^2) \equiv \frac{E(\text{R}U_t^2)}{N}$ (see equation 38). Based on these relationships, equation 92 changes slightly. In general, there is a certain reason to consider that

$$p(\text{R}U_t) = 1 - \frac{\sigma(\text{R}\bar{U}_t)^2}{E(\text{R}\bar{U}_t^2)} \quad (93)$$

□

According to the **central limit theorem** (see Pólya, 1920) there are circumstances where the distribution of the sum (or average) of a large number of random variables will be approximately normal, regardless of the underlying distribution. Roughly, the central limit theorem is one important reason why many statistical procedures work.

Example. Simple Moving Average (SMA) Often, the price data of a share during a certain period of time are used to calculate something like a moving average. One very simple form of a moving average of the price of a share is the so called simple moving average (SMA). The simple moving average is the arithmetic mean i.e. of the prices of a share and is often published as a t = 200-day line. For this reason, the closing prices of the previous 199 days and the current price of a share are added and divided by 200. The exact probability associated with the price of a share is given as

$$p(\text{R}U_{t=200}) = 1 - \frac{\sigma(\text{R}\bar{U}_{t=200})^2}{E(\text{R}\bar{U}_{t=200}^2)} \quad (94)$$

In point of fact, the method discussed before provides a rather simple approach to the statistical analysis of time series.⁶ Furthermore, theoretically, it seems to be possible to automate the decryption process of encrypted data. The probability that a certain pattern occurs in the last t=200 measurements can be calculated precisely according to equation 94 with all the consequences.

⁶Anderson, Theodore W. The statistical analysis of time series. John Wiley & Sons, 2011.

3.3. Approximate probability of an event

Euler's number e , rediscovered by the Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler (1707 – 1783), is also known as Napier's Constant for John Napier of Merchiston (1550-1617) and was first discovered in 1683 by Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli. Under some circumstances, the sample average of the first N samples. For large enough sample size N , the distribution of the sample average $\bar{R}U_t$ gets arbitrarily close to the normal distribution (central limit (see Pólya, 1920) theorem (CLT)) with mean $E(RU_t)$ and variance $\frac{\sigma(RU_t)^2}{N}$. With this background in mind, the probability of an event can be determined approximately.

Theorem 3 (Approximate probability of an event).

$$p(RU_t) \equiv e^{-\left(\frac{\sigma(RU_t)^2}{E(RU_t^2)}\right)} \quad (95)$$

Proof by direct proof. In correspondence with equation 37 and equation 89 it is

$$p(RU_t) \equiv \left(1 - \frac{\sigma(RU_t)^2}{E(RU_t^2)}\right) \quad (96)$$

or

$$p(RU_t) \equiv \left(1 - \frac{N \times \sigma(RU_t)^2}{N \times RU_t \times E(RU_t)}\right)^{\frac{1}{N}} \quad (97)$$

Increasing the number of randomly generated variables (sample size N grows) changes equation 97 only slightly. It is

$$p(RU_t) \equiv \left(1 - \frac{N \times \sigma(RU_t)^2}{N \times RU_t \times E(RU_t)}\right)^{N \times \frac{1}{N}} \quad (98)$$

In agreement with the known elementary calculus (DeGroot and Schervish, 2005, p. 195), as the sample size N goes to positive infinity ($N \rightarrow +\infty$), it is

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \left(1 - \frac{RU_t}{N}\right)^N \equiv e^{-RU_t} \quad (99)$$

Equation 98 becomes

$$p(RU_t) \equiv \left(1 - \frac{N \times \sigma(RU_t)^2}{N \times RU_t \times E(RU_t)}\right)^{N \times \frac{1}{N}} \equiv \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)^{N \times \frac{1}{N} \times \left(-\frac{N \times \sigma(RU_t)^2}{RU_t \times E(RU_t)}\right)} \equiv e^{-\left(\frac{\sigma(RU_t)^2}{E(RU_t^2)}\right)} \quad (100)$$

□

3.4. Causal relationship k

The causal relationship k as a measure of a causal relationship between events is derived (see Barukčić, 2021) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 k(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j)}{\sqrt{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_i)^2 \times \sigma(\mathbf{R}W_j)^2}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j)}{\sigma(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times \sigma(\mathbf{R}W_j)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{(\mathbf{R}U_i \times \mathbf{R}W_j) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{\sqrt{((\mathbf{R}U_i)^2 \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j)^2 \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{(\mathbf{R}U_i \times \mathbf{R}W_j) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{(\mathbf{R}U_i \times \mathbf{R}W_j) \times \sqrt{((p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{(p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{\sqrt{((p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{101}$$

The relative frequency has no influence on the causal relationship k and does not lead to logical inconsistency.

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$k = \frac{(p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{\sqrt{((p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}} \tag{102}$$

Multiplying equation 102 by the term $((\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j))$, it is

$$k = \frac{((\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j)) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{((\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j)) \times \sqrt{((p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}} \tag{103}$$

or

$$k = \frac{((\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j)) \times (p(\mathbf{R}U_i, \mathbf{R}W_j) - (p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times p(\mathbf{R}W_j)))}{\sqrt{(\mathbf{R}U_i)^2 \times ((p(\mathbf{R}U_i) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}U_i))) \times (\mathbf{R}W_j)^2 \times (p(\mathbf{R}W_j) \times (1 - p(\mathbf{R}W_j))))}} \tag{104}$$

According to equation 11 it is

$$\mathbf{R}U_i = \left(\frac{\mathbf{R}\bar{U}_i}{p(\mathbf{R}\bar{U}_i)} \right) \tag{105}$$

and it is

$${}_R W_i = \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \quad (106)$$

The relative frequencies can be used without any restriction in order to calculate the causal relationship k . Equation 104 becomes

$$k = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right) \times \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right) \right) \times (p({}_R U_i, {}_R W_j) - (p({}_R U_i) \times p({}_R W_j)))}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{{}_R \bar{U}_i}{p({}_R \bar{U}_i)} \right)^2 \times (p({}_R U_i) \times (1 - p({}_R U_i))) \times \left(\frac{{}_R \bar{W}_j}{p({}_R \bar{W}_j)} \right)^2 \times (p({}_R W_j) \times (1 - p({}_R W_j)))}} \quad (107)$$

□

4. Discussion

Not surprisingly, it might appear intuitively obvious that science aims to provide us with causal knowledge of objective reality and that causal claims are an integral part of science as such. However, there continues to be an active and lively scientific debate on whether causation can play any legitimate role in science? Thus far, in discussing the role of causation in science, an author may choose one of several different approaches. In contrast to contemporary defenders anti causality in science, even the methods of probability theory can be used to uncover the deterministic relationship between cause (C) and effect (E). How then, can we describe the relationship between the cause and an effect E? Taking a somewhat broader view, the presence or occurrence of a cause, an effect or of a cause and an effect can be described by probability measures too. In particular, the presence of a cause might raise (or at least change) the probability of its own effect and potentially vice versa too. Nonetheless, discussions of tension between causation and the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics motivated various (see Barukčić, 1989) authors, including Patrick Suppes (1922-2014) (see Suppes, 1970), to develop a probabilistic accounts of causation (see Suppes, 1970). Meanwhile, defenders of causation in science expose themselves more and more to the threat of being generally and unreasonably discredited as causal imperialists. Such ideologically misguided dead-beat arguments have in the end no influence on simple facts. The relationship between cause and effect exists objectively and real and independent of the various attempts to describe the relationship between cause and effect adequately.

5. Conclusion

‘Probability theory is of help to describe the relationship between cause and effect.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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